

Research Article

Innovation in Stone

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Abstract: Granite is a phaneritic intrusive igneous rock with quartz, alkali feldspar, and plagioclase as the main constituents. It is made up of silica-rich magma and alkali metal oxides that cools and hardens slowly underground. It is found in igneous intrusions throughout the Earth's continental crust. These range in size from a few millimeters wide dikes to hundreds of square kilometers of batholiths. Granite is part of a wider group of granitic rocks known as granitoids, which are made up mostly of coarse-grained quartz and feldspars in various proportions. The relative ratios of quartz, alkali feldspar, and plagioclase are used to classify these rocks, with real granite denoting granitic rocks rich in quartz and alkali feldspar. Although most granitic rocks include mica or amphibole minerals, a handful have essentially no dark minerals. This paper will review the creativity and innovation in stone.

Keywords: Creativity; Innovation; Stone; Quartz; Silica

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1. INTRODUCTION

Granite is almost usually huge, hard, and tough. Granite's characteristics have made it a popular building material throughout history. The name "granite" derives from the Latin word granum, which means "grain," and refers to the coarse-grained structure of a fully crystalline rock. Feldspar, quartz, mica, and amphibole minerals create an interlocking, slightly equigranular matrix of feldspar and quartz, with dispersed darker biotite mica and amphibole peppering the lighter colour minerals in granitic rocks. When certain individual crystals phenocrysts are bigger than the groundmass, the texture is described as porphyritic. Granite porphyry is a granitic rock having a porphyritic structure. Granitoid is a name used to describe lighter-colored, coarse-grained igneous rocks. Identification of certain kinds of granitoids requires a petrographic investigation. Depending on their composition, granites can be primarily white, pink, or grey in hue.

Nowadays, concrete is the most frequently utilised construction material on the planet. It's employed in a variety of applications, including buildings, bridges, walkways, highway pavements, housing construction, dams, and more. The proportions of the various components in a strong and lasting concrete are crucial. More voids mean less strength and durability, whereas more cement paste means more shrinkage and less durability.

Strength and porosity are affected by gradation and the ratio of fine to coarse particles. The mix design should also provide the necessary concrete workability to avoid segregation and facilitate installation. A typical concrete mix has 10 to 15 percent cement, 25 to 30 percents and, 40 to 45 percent aggregate,

and 15 to 20 percent water. To increase the durability of concrete, entrained air (5–7%) is also injected. Concrete should have sufficient compressive and flexural strength to withstand the applied loads. It should also be durable in order to extend its design life and lower maintenance expenses.

In general, durable concrete will with stand freeze-thaw cycles, abrasion, sulphate reactions, UV radiation, saltwater, the alkali-silica reaction, and chlorides. Granite powder, a waste product of the granite polishing industry, has properties that are similar to pozzolanic materials like silica fume, fly ash, slag, and others, making it a viable material for use in concrete. These compounds can be used to fill voids in concrete by replacing sand. Granite powder is a powdered residue of granite stone crushing and polishing. Marble tops, terrazzo, granite pavers, and stone scrapes and discards all contribute to its production. If not properly collected and kept, fine granite powder can readily become airborne, causing health issues and pollution.

2. CHALLENGE SUMMARY

The topic of problems for geoscientists are addressed using the discipline of environmental geology. "What?" "Where?" "When?" and "Why?" are all questions that's common for a journalist seeks to a solution, but "How" isn't one in every of them. This corresponds to a geoscientist's understanding of the geography and structure of earth materials, similarly because the processes that formed the. The "How?" question is maybe the foremost fascinating for scientists. When considering the fashionable environment an additional question is often asked: "Who?" because Man's influence is becoming a more significant environmental component, in most cases depleting and destroying natural resources. The constant reinstating of geology's vital role to society could be a recurring subject.

2.1 *Environmental Change Recorded by The Paraná Delta*

The first example comes from South America, where land-use change and forest loss are major concerns worldwide. However, during a recent visit to Sweden (2007), Brazilian President Lula da Silva stated emphatically that "the twenty-first century is for those countries that did not get their dreams fulfilled in the previous century, and Brazil will not miss its moment." A European Union research project is currently assessing climate change implications on a continental scale in South America. The reviewers, however, rejected a proposal emphasizing the geological control of previous climatic change, stating that it "underestimated the relevance of climatic models to assess the response of the catchment area to climate change". In other words, models will be utilised for self-calibration and will be considered more reliable than the reality provided by a geological baseline.

2.2 *Deep Basins in The Baltic Sea*

The Baltic Sea, whose deep basins are regularly oxygen-depleted ("anoxic"), is an analogous example. The oxygen available for decomposing organic material, primarily from plankton blooms, is limited due to stratification and poor bottom water regeneration. These are thought to have risen as a result of increased land- based nutrient supply, particularly phosphorus (P) from sewage and agricultural waste. When mixing does occur, as it did in 1995 after a major storm, the changes in both oxygen and phosphorus can be fairly substantial. Such natural "experiments" have prompted oceanographers at Göteborg University to propose a technical solution involving large-scale wind turbines pumping down oxygenated surface waters.

3. RESULTS

This study's experimental results show that replacing some of the sand in concrete with granite powder (GP) or iron powder (IP) improves its compressive, flexural, and tensile strength. The physical and chemical contributions of granite powder and iron powder in concrete are highly dependent on particle size. Because granite powder has a smaller particle size than sand, it was able to fill the voids between sand particles in the same way that sand particles fill the voids between coarse aggregates, resulting in fewer voids and higher density and strength. Furthermore, because the particle size is smaller than that of sand, the surface area will be larger. Because granite powder has a higher surface area than sand, the concrete is expected to have higher strength due to more bonded areas with hydrating cement. Although granite powder has less silicon oxide content than sand and no tall granite powder will react chemically with cement, the filler effect will improve the concrete. In the case of iron powder, the increase in strength can be attributed to a slight increase in particle fineness, particularly in the smaller diameter particles. It could also be due to the higher percentage of iron oxide in the iron powder.

The results of the tests revealed that a 10% granite powder ratio resulted in the greatest increase in compressive and flexural strength. Beyond 10%, the increase was less. Beyond this percentage, it appears that the filling effect of granite powder is not optimised. In most cases, an optimal size distribution in concrete results in higher density and fewer voids. If the particle size distribution is not optimal, the concrete will have more voids and thus be weaker. More hydrating cement appears to be required to bond these areas as the surface area increases. If the water-cement ratio and added admixtures are insufficient to hydrate enough cement, the increased surface area of granite powder will not be fully bonded, resulting in less strength with higher granite powder ratios. The results of iron powder showed that as the iron powder ratio increased, so did the compressive, flexural, and tensile strength. In this study, the maximum ratio of iron powder as partial replacement of sand was limited to 20%, so trends in the change in mechanical properties of concrete with ratios greater than 20% are not available. However, the results for compressive strength and split tensile strength appear to plateau at 20%. The increase in flexural strength was still noticeable at 20%. The gradation, the surface geometry, and the presence of higher percentages of iron oxide are likely reasons for the increase in strength of iron powder concrete.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, the following conclusions can be stated; the concrete mix made with granite powder and iron powder as partial replacements for sand demonstrated similar workability and fluidity to standard concrete mixes. The addition of granite powder as a partial replacement for sand increased the compressive strength of concrete. When compared to other ratios, using 10% granite powder in concrete produced the highest increase in compressive strength.

The compressive, flexural, and tensile strengths of mixes containing iron powder increased as the iron powder ratio increased. Unlike granite powder, the increase in strength continued to concrete as the iron powder ratio increased. The increase in flexural strength was more pronounced when compared to compressive and tensile strengths. This research focused on the mechanical properties of concrete with granite powder and iron powder, as well as its workability and fluidity. This study did not look at the long-term performance of concrete with granite powder and iron powder. Durability is critical for the proper use of this material in both structural and non-structural applications, and it will be investigated further in a future study.

References

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